

**MORPHOLOGY OF THE FIRST INSTAR LARVA
OF *MILTOGRAMMA PARDALINA* (ROHDENDORF, 1934)
(DIPTERA: SARCOPHAGIDAE)**

**MORFOLOGIA LARWY I STADIUM
MILTOGRAMMA PARDALINA (ROHDENDORF, 1934)
(DIPTERA: SARCOPHAGIDAE)**

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ABSTRACT. The first instar larva is described for *Miltogramma pardalina* (ROHDENDORF, 1934). Using a combination of light microscopy and scanning electron microscopy, the habitus is documented along with all important exoskeletal and cephaloskeletal structures. The first instar larva of *M. pardalina* fits well within the morphological diversity of the genus *Miltogramma* MEIGEN and is the most similar to larvae of *M. margiana* (ROHDENDORF, 1925) and *M. punctata* MEIGEN, 1824. Larvae of these species share at least six larval character states but all of them may be treated as typical for ancestral larva of Miltogramminae and cannot be interpreted as synapomorphies. Information about larval morphology of *M. pardalina* will assist future evolutionary studies of the genus *Miltogramma* based on the application of methods of the next generation sequencing.

KEY WORDS: Miltogramminae, flesh flies, SEM, the Middle East

INTRODUCTION

Recent molecular phylogenies of Miltogramminae have given the opportunity of verification of hypotheses on various aspects of the evolution of larval morphology in this taxon (PIWCZYŃSKI *et al.* 2017, BUENAVENTURA *et al.* 2019). During the last two decades, integration of various techniques of documentation have provided extensive high-quality information on the larval morphology of the subfamily (e.g. SZPILA 2010; SZPILA *et al.* 2013, 2017; SZPILA *et al.* 2017), but existing data mostly concern European species (SZPILA 2010). Information about taxa occurring in areas with the highest diversity of the Miltogramminae, like the Middle East and Central Asia (PAPE 1996), is only slowly accumulating (SZPILA *et al.* 2008, 2013, 2017; PAPE *et al.* 2012; SZPILA *et al.* 2017), and data from taxa in less diverse regions like the Neotropics and Australasia are almost absent. A considerable part of the miltogrammine morphospace remains unknown (SZPILA *et al.* 2017), which complicates understanding traits suspected to be involved in the diversification of larval morphology, especially in case of species-rich kleptoparasitic genera like *Miltogramma* MEIGEN. This genus contains more than 100 valid species (PAPE 1996; VERVES *et al.* 2008) and is the largest in the subfamily. Under alternative classifications, *Miltogramma sensu* PAPE (1996) holds a status of subtribe (Miltogrammatina) and contains some 8–11 separate genera (ROHDENDORF 1967; VERVES 1989, 1994). Unfortunately, representatives of most of these were not included in the recent molecular studies of miltogrammine phylogeny (*Achaetocephalon* ROHDENDORF, *Aleximyia* ROHDENDORF, *Anacanthotecum* ROHDENDORF, *Cylindrothecum* ROHDENDORF, *Miltogrammoides* ROHDENDORF, *Efflatounomyia* ROHDENDORF, *Rhynchapodacra* ROHDENDORF) (PIWCZYŃSKI *et al.* 2017, BUENAVENTURA *et al.* 2019), and often also their larval morphology remains unknown (*Achaetocephalon*, *Aleximyia*, *Miltogrammoides*, *Efflatounomyia*, *Rhynchapodacra*). The aim of the present publication is to provide for the first time information about the first instar larval morphology of *Miltogramma pardalina* (ROHDENDORF, 1934), representing the genus *Efflatounomyia sensu* VERVES (1989, 1994). This group contains four valid species distributed in desert habitats reaching from the Middle East to Mongolia (ROHDENDORF *et al.* 1980, PAPE 1996). Adult flies are characterised by a peculiar long proboscis and exposed small furca-like remains of the ptilinum at lunula (ROHDENDORF *et al.* 1980; VERVES 1989, 1994; Fig. 1C–E). VERVES (1989) in his hand-drawn phylogenetic tree grouped *Efflatounomyia* together with *Pediasomyia* and *Rhynchapodacra* as the sister clade to all other Miltogrammatina (*Miltogramma* + *Euphyto* TOWNSEND *sensu* PAPE 1996). Information about first instar larval morphology of *M. pardalina* will assist future evolutionary studies of the genus *Miltogramma* based on the application of next generation sequencing methodology.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

One female was collected in the dry river bed of Nahal Zin, in the northern part of Negev Desert, Israel (30°50'13"N 35°08'23"E) (Fig. 1A–G). To obtain larvae, the female was kept alive in a 3 ml Eppendorf tube with a finely perforated cover. During the following day, the female spontaneously and repeatedly larviposited. After the death of the female, additional larvae were extracted from her abdomen by gently squeezing the abdomen. Larvae were

killed by soaking in hot water (about 95°C) to avoid deformation and stored in 70% ethanol. Preserved larvae were slide-mounted in Hoyer's medium for light microscopy.

Preparation for scanning electron microscopy (SEM) involved dehydration through 80, 90 and 99.5% ethanol and critical-point drying in CO₂. The larvae were eventually coated with platinum. SEM pictures were taken with the use of a JEOL JSM 6335F field emission microscope. Light microscope illustrations were produced from photographs made with the use of a digital NIKON 8400 camera mounted on NIKON ECLIPSE E200 microscope.

Fig. 1A–G. *Miltogramma pardalina*, female. A – habitus, lateral view. B – abdomen, dorsal view. C – head, lateral view. D – head, frontal view. E – head, dorsal view. F – right wing. G – labels. Red arrow points on furca.

The female specimen was subsequently pinned and labelled. Identification was made using the key of ROHDENDORF *et* VERVES (1980). The adult female and all larvae and microscope slides have been deposited in the Department of Ecology and Biogeography, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Toruń, Poland (DEB). Data from labels are given verbatim, with lines separated by a slash (/) and individual labels by a double slash (//).

Larval terminology follows Courtney *et al.* (2000) with a few modifications proposed by SZPILA *et PAPE* (2007) and SZPILA (2010).

Fig. 2A–J. First instar larva of *Miltogramma pardalina*. A – anterior part, antero-lateral view. B – anterior part, lateral view; C – anterior part, dorsal view; D – anterior part, ventral view. E – antennal complex. F – maxillary palpus. G – ventral organ. H – KEILIN's organ (on t1); I – first and second abdominal segments, lateral view; J – second abdominal segment, lateral papilla.

Abbreviations: a1–2, first and second abdominal segments; an, antennal complex; abr, antennal basal ring; and, antennal dome; asb, anterior spinose band; lcw, lateral creeping welt; mh, mouthhook; mp, maxillary palpus; ns1, first additional sensillum coeloconicum; ns2, second additional sensillum coeloconicum; sb1–3, sensilla basiconica 1–3; sc1–3, sensilla coeloconica 1–3; vo, ventral organ.

Fig. 3A–I. First instar larva of *Miltogramma pardalina*. A – second and third thoracic segments, dorsal view. B – second thoracic segment, dorsal view, anterior spinose band. C – second thoracic segment, dorsal view, dorsal papilla. D – second abdominal segment, ventral view. E – second abdominal segment, anterior proleg. F – anal division, posterior view. G – anal division, posterior spiracle. H – anal division, ventral view. I – anal division, anal complex.

Abbreviations: a1, first abdominal segment; at, anal tuft; apr, anterior proleg; asb, anterior spinose band; ao, anal opening; ap, anal papilla; dp, dorsal papilla; lcw, lateral creeping welt; p1–7, papillae p1–7; sp, posterior spiracle; pt, peristigmatic tuft; t1–3, thoracic segments.

RESULTS

Material examined: 21 first instar larvae, all from the same female: “ISRAEL, Negev / Nahal Zin n. Road 227 / 15.05.2006 / leg. K. SZPILA // M17,06 NH / 15.05.06. // *Miltogramma* / *pardalina* / (Rohdendorf, 1934) / det. K. SZPILA”.

The body of the first instar of *M. pardalina* follows the general pattern of Calypttratae in being divided into a bilobed pseudocephalon (pc), three thoracic segments (t1–t3), seven abdominal segments (a1–a7), and the anal division (ad) carrying the anus and posterior spiracles (Fig. 4A).

Pseudocephalon. Antennal complex (an) large, with clearly differentiated, large antennal dome (and) and a high basal ring (abr) (Figs. 2A–E, 4B); maxillary palpus (mp) shaped as a protuberance distinctly differentiated from surrounding surface of pseudocephalon, first sensillum basiconicum (sb1) distinctly elongated (Fig. 2F); ventral organ (vo) on small cylindrical protuberance (Fig. 2D, G); oral ridges absent (Fig. 2D); remaining surface of pseudocephalon with numerous warts and longitudinal cuticular ridges (Fig. 2A–D).

Cephaloskeleton. Labrum (lb) slightly curved downward, with clearly differentiated, narrower anterior part, and pointed tip (Fig. 4B); mouthhooks (mh) with widened basal part and strong, hook-like anterior part (Fig. 4B), anterior part of mouthhooks with single, pointed tip (Figs. 2A, B, D; 4B); intermediate sclerite (is) ventral to parastomal bars (pb) in lateral view (Fig. 4B), transverse junction of intermediate sclerite in lateral view shaped as a triangular protuberance (Fig. 4B), in ventral view intermediate sclerite much longer than wide, with broad transverse junction (Fig. 4C); parastomal bar (pb) fused with vertical plate (vp) distinctly above lower margin of ventral cornu (Fig. 4B); vertical plate broader than dorsal cornu (dc), width of ventral cornu (vc) difficult to define (Fig. 4B); dorsal bridge absent.

Thoracic segments. Anterior spinose bands with 3–4 (lateral surfaces) to 10–11 (dorsal surface of t2) rows of spines (Fig. 2A–D); spines wide and scale-like, mostly with apical margin serrated (Fig. 2C, 3B); thoracic segments (t1–t3) with longitudinal cuticular ridges on all surfaces (Figs. 2A–D, 3A), antero-ventral margin of the first thoracic segment with two very small (but distinct) protuberances directed laterally (Fig. 2A–D); sensilla of KEILIN'S organ short (Fig. 2H).

Fig. 4A–C. First instar larva of *Miltogramma pardalina*. A – habitus, lateral view. B – cephaloskeleton, lateral view; C – cephaloskeleton, ventral view.

Abbreviations: a1–7, abdominal segments; ad, anal division; pc, pseudocephalon; dc, dorsal cornu; is, intermediate sclerite; lb, labrum; mh, mouthhook; pb, parastomal bar; t1–3, thoracic segments; vc, ventral cornu; vp, vertical plate.

Abdominal segments. Anterior spinose band on abdominal segments (a1–a7) with 3–4 to 10–11 rows of spines (including spines on ventral creeping welts), bands complete (Fig. 4A); posterior spinose bands present on segments a3–a7, bands incomplete, interrupted on lateral surfaces; spines broad with serrated tips (Fig. 3D, E); lateral creeping welts (lcw) well developed and sparsely covered by spines (Figs. 2I, 3D); ventral creeping welts indistinct, anterior proleg (apr) well visible (Fig. 3D, E); lateral and dorsal surfaces of segments a1–a7 with longitudinal cuticular ridges (Fig. 2I, J); lateral papilla with short sensillum (Fig. 2J). Anal division. Anterior spinose band incomplete, interrupted on lateral surfaces (Fig. 3F, H); dorsal and lateral surfaces of anal division (ad) with cuticular ridges (Fig. 3F, H, I); papillae surrounding spiracular field (p1–p7) visible as small protuberances with a sensillum on top (Fig. 3F); margin around spiracular field with indistinct row of warts/spines (Fig. 3F); posterior spiracles (ps) with four broad peristigmatic tufts (pt), with distal margin shallowly cut to form three to several irregular branches (Fig. 3G); anal papillae rounded (Fig. 3H, I); anal tuft (at) with numerous spines (Fig. 3I).

DISCUSSION

The morphology of the first instar larva of *M. pardalina* fits well within the morphological diversity of the genus *Miltogramma sensu* PAPE (1996) by displaying a set of character states relating to the configuration of the cephaloskeleton, which are also found in other species of the genus *Miltogramma* (SZPILA 2010): 1) intermediate sclerite broad in ventral view, 2) parastomal bars fused with the vertical plate of the basal sclerite distinctly above (dorsal to) the lower margin of the ventral cornu, 3) basal sclerite higher than long. The morphology of the first instar larva of *M. pardalina* is most similar to that of *M. margiana* (ROHDENDORF, 1925) and *M. punctata* MEIGEN, 1824. First instar larvae of these species share the following character states: 1) antennal complex with oval, slightly elongated dome and high basal ring, 2) maxillary palpus with only the first sensillum basiconicum elongated, 3) tip of mouthhooks hook-like, pointed, with single tip, 4) interband surface of all thoracic segments with longitudinal cuticular ridges, 5) dorsal and lateral surfaces of all abdominal segments with longitudinal cuticular ridges, 6) spiracular field flat with well exposed posterior spiracles. None of the abovementioned six character states can be interpreted as synapomorphic for these three species, and they are probably ancestral larval character states for the Miltogramminae (SZPILA 2010, PIWCZYŃSKI *et al.* 2017). However, on the phylogenetic tree reconstructed using molecular data (COI, cytB, ND4, Ef-1 α), *M. margiana* and *M. punctata* group together with high support under both maximum likelihood and Bayesian inference methods (PIWCZYŃSKI *et al.* 2017). The question of a possible close relationship of *M. pardalina* with *M. margiana* and *M. punctata* should be explored by more inclusive studies of Miltogramminae phylogeny with application of next generation sequencing methods and with a broader taxon sampling of representatives of *Miltogramma*.

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* *Editorial remarks:*

* Papers of the 35th volume of *Dipteron* are dedicated to the late AGNIESZKA DRABER-MOŃKO.